

1 **The ocean carbon sink enhances countries' inclusive wealth and reduces the cost of national**
2 **climate policies**

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15

16 **Abstract**

17 Improving our understanding of future ocean carbon uptake requires a nuanced understanding of the
18 value of the annual ocean sink. Here, we combine an abatement cost-based approach and a climate
19 damage-based approach to assess the value of the annual ocean sink. The former shows that the
20 aggregate cost of national climate policies could increase by up to USD 80 billion if the ocean carbon
21 sink weakens by 10 percent. As a complementary perspective, the damage-based approach shows
22 that the annual ocean carbon sink contributes between USD 300 billion and USD 2,332 billion to
23 countries' inclusive wealth. Despite the conceptual appeal of the damage-based approach for its
24 potential insights into regional wealth redistribution, uncertainties in national social cost of carbon
25 estimates make it less reliable than the abatement cost-based approach, which in turn provides more
26 reliable estimates for a fiscal cost assessment of improved monitoring services of the ocean carbon
27 sink.

28

29 **1 Introduction**

30 Since the preindustrial era, the ocean has absorbed roughly 26 percent of anthropogenic CO₂
31 emissions [1], reducing climate change impacts and providing, in addition to many other services, a
32 considerable societal value as a carbon sink. What exactly the societal value of this natural ocean sink
33 is and how it is distributed across different regions needs to be quantified, though. This information is
34 relevant (i) for inclusive wealth accounting and sustainable development assessments, (ii) for justifying
35 improving the accuracy of ocean carbon sink estimates and thus forecasting potential weakening of
36 the ocean carbon sink, and (iii) for assessing deliberate efforts to increase the ocean sink through
37 marine carbon dioxide removal (CDR) technologies.

38

39 Various studies investigate the annual, cumulative or future amount of anthropogenic CO₂ taken up
40 by the ocean. We instead focus on estimating the value of the annual ocean carbon sink, based on
41 different CO₂ price estimates, and using two different valuation approaches. On the one hand, we
42 consider a cost-benefit approach, taking the perspective that the ocean carbon sink reduces climate
43 damages. On the other hand, we use a cost-effectiveness approach, taking the perspective that the
44 ocean sink influences the remaining anthropogenic CO₂ emissions budget, and in turn the CO₂
45 abatement cost. Accordingly, we combine a climate-change-damage-based approach with an
46 abatement-cost-based approach to valuing the ocean carbon sink. The former utilizes information on
47 the social cost of carbon (SCC), i.e., the marginal damage of an additional ton of CO₂ being released
48 into the atmosphere, and in turn the marginal avoided damage of an additional ton of CO₂ being
49 absorbed by a carbon sink. The latter utilizes information on marginal abatement costs. In a stylized
50 and optimized global climate policy, the two approaches would coincide, since the marginal
51 abatement cost would be equated across countries (either via a global carbon tax or international
52 emissions trading) at the level of the SCC, i.e., the sum of SCCs for all countries. In reality (and in
53 applied work), the two approaches do not align, since the remaining carbon budget is not derived
54 from a global cost-benefit analysis but rather determined as part of national priorities and a political
55 bargaining process, with different countries using different instruments to reduce their CO₂ and other
56 greenhouse gas emissions. Hence, applying the two approaches to valuing the ocean sink sheds light
57 on conflicting outcomes depending on the stringency of the overall climate policy ambition.

58

59 Applying the climate-damage-based approach places the valuation of the annual ocean carbon sink in
60 the natural capital and inclusive wealth (IW) framework [2, 3, 4, 5]. A value estimate derived as the
61 present value of the entire future path of the ocean carbon sink provides an estimate of the total value
62 of ocean carbon sink while a value estimate of the carbon sink in a given year provides an estimate of
63 the ocean carbon sink contribution to comprehensive investment [2]. Comprehensive investment

64 measures the change in IW. Non-negative comprehensive investment, i.e. the aggregate value of
65 investments and disinvestments in all natural and human-made capital stocks, is required to achieve
66 (weak) sustainable development [6]. IW assessments (used to measure sustainable development, i.e.
67 the change in comprehensive investment) are applied in the United Nations (UN) Inclusive Wealth
68 Reports [7,8,9], but do not yet include the wealth contribution of the ocean carbon sink. The United
69 States have recently launched a draft National Strategy to improve its statistical description of
70 economic activity and development by accounting for the wealth contributions of water, air, and other
71 natural assets following the IW approach, but not yet the value of the ocean carbon sink [10].

72

73 In terms of valuing the ocean carbon sink, applying the SCC allows us to measure the damage avoided
74 in a given year, i.e. the mitigated reduction in comprehensive investment resulting from CO₂
75 emissions. Canu et al. [11] apply this approach to value the carbon sink in the Mediterranean Sea,
76 estimating an annual value between 127 and 1,722 M EUR (2011)/year. However, different countries
77 are affected differently by climate change and hence it is assumed that climate change will result in
78 wealth redistribution [12]. Bertram et al. [13] account for this aspect by applying the country social
79 cost of carbon (CSCC) in their assessment of coastal blue carbon ecosystem sequestration. They show,
80 for example, that annual carbon sequestration in Australia's coastal ecosystems has a global value of
81 about USD 25 billion per year, of which almost USD 23 billion are received abroad. However, the global
82 annual amount of carbon sequestration attributable to coastal ecosystems globally is rather with
83 about 81 MtC rather small [13].

84

85 The uncertainty about climate-change impacts on ecosystems, human health and economies was the
86 main reason for defining temperature ceilings as part of the Paris Agreement (keeping the global
87 temperature increase well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels and ideally limiting it to 1.5 °C). This
88 approach translates into the objective to cost-efficiently achieve compliance with the temperature
89 ceiling, determining the marginal abatement cost, i.e., the CO₂ price that would achieve compliance
90 with the temperature ceiling (i.e., the willingness to pay for compliance with such a temperature
91 ceiling, see Cross-Chapter Box 5 in [14]). Accordingly, implemented CO₂ tax levels or observed CO₂
92 prices on emissions trading markets can be used as information for valuation purposes, again allowing
93 to derive information on comprehensive investment, though with a price information implicitly
94 including information on the willingness to pay to achieve emissions reductions targets.

95 However, CO₂ pricing instruments are not everywhere in place, and in many cases, for example in the
96 European Union, CO₂ pricing instruments cover only a fraction of the emissions in the region. Hence,
97 economic models have to be used to estimate regional CO₂ prices consistent with the region's

98 emissions reduction goals. Rehdanz et al. [15] assessed the integration of the ocean anthropogenic
99 carbon sink into a hypothetical carbon market, using model-based estimates for the anthropogenic
100 part of the regional ocean sink [16].

101

102 With regard to the integration of (attributed) carbon sinks into climate policy and emissions trading,
103 it should be noted that only those land-based carbon sinks that are managed and therefore considered
104 additional are included in climate policy. And even for these, there remain several issues regarding
105 the appropriate accounting of land sinks in the greenhouse gas (GHG) inventories of countries [17].
106 However, also natural, non-additional, services are of value. Accordingly, it is uncontested that the
107 wealth contribution achieved via carbon sequestration from large forest areas of a specific land-locked
108 country should be considered in inclusive wealth and sustainable development assessments. In a
109 similar fashion, the fractional ocean carbon sink of a coastal country should be considered as well.
110 Furthermore, any attribution of the ocean carbon sink as part of international climate policy
111 frameworks does not necessarily imply a potential buy-out from ambitious emissions reductions, as
112 the implications for emissions reduction commitments depend on the particular baseline considered
113 for the ocean carbon sink. In turn, the attribution of a fraction of the ocean sink to a particular country
114 could result in additional responsibility or even liability, i.e. the requirement to increase emission
115 reduction efforts in that country if the ocean sink were to weaken in the future.

116

117 Our article aims to shed light on the two approaches, the climate-damage-based approach and the
118 abatement-cost-based approach, and how they can be combined to achieve a more nuanced
119 understanding of the contribution of annual ocean carbon sink to wealth and climate policy.

120 **2 Results**

121 **2.1 Regional attribution of the ocean sink**

122 Which components of the ocean carbon sink should be included in such a valuation and how these
123 should be attributed to countries are a study object on its own. We use for our valuation the model-
124 based derived global ocean CO₂ sink of 2.8 (SD ±0.4) GtC (in the year 2022) from the global carbon
125 budget [1] and assign it proportional to the EEZ area of countries. With this area-based approach,
126 about 59 percent of the ocean carbon sink are attributed to the high seas (see methods). For the ocean
127 carbon sink attributed to countries, Figure 1 shows the 10 states (or confederation of states) with the
128 largest attributed ocean sink. Note that we included in the European Union (EU) also Norway and
129 Iceland (EU29) due to the joint climate policy of these states with the EU. The figure shows the large
130 gains from overseas territories of the EU29, the United States, Australia and Great Britain. Within the
131 EU29, the largest attribution resulting from overseas territories is achieved by France and Denmark

132 (both achieving about 96 percent of their attributed ocean sink via overseas territories). Furthermore,
133 note that this approach favors small islands states like for example Kiribati (KIR), an island nation in
134 the tropical Pacific Ocean, with approximately 726 km² land area and a 3,550,000-km² EEZ located in
135 the Pacific upwelling area, putting it on the tenth place in Figure 1 (and attributing a much larger share
136 of the ocean carbon sink compared to a carbon-flux based approach, see methods).

137

138 Figure 1 about here

139

140 **2.2 CO₂ Price Estimates**

141 Figure 2 shows the various CO₂ price estimates at the global and at the national level, the latter
142 displayed for ten major industrialized and developing regions in international climate policy [18]
143 (Supplementary Figure SMF1 shows the corresponding information for the countries and regions with
144 the highest CO₂ emissions in the fossil and industrial sector).

145

146 Figure 2 about here

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148

149 There are substantial differences between the two climate change damage estimates: 227.28
150 USD/tCO₂ (SD 14.95) based on Dell et al. [19], abbreviated DJO, and 29.17 USD/tCO₂ (SD 3.69) based
151 on Tol [20], abbreviated Tol (Figure 2).

152

153 However, even for the rather large DJO-CSCC estimates, in 6 out of the 10 countries shown in Figure
154 2, the marginal abatement cost exceeds the country-specific marginal damage for both NDC
155 ambitions, indicating higher-than-optimal abatement efforts for the country from a national, non-
156 cooperative perspective. For these countries, the NDCs apparently include some concern for climate
157 damage that occurs outside their borders. Unfortunately, this does not hold true for China, the United
158 States, India, or Russia, where country-specific marginal abatement costs are below their DJO-CSCC
159 estimates. These countries contribute about 59 percent of the projected CO₂ emissions in 2030 in our
160 study.

161

162 Overall, in 106 countries (of the 146 used in the abatement-based approach), the national CO₂ prices
163 – marginal abatement costs for the given NDCs under high ambition – exceed the DJO-CSCC estimate.
164 For the Tol-CSCC estimates, in 107 countries, the national CO₂ prices exceed the CSCC estimate. In
165 turn, that means that even for the comparatively low Tol-CSCC estimates, not every country's marginal
166 abatement cost exceeds its country-specific marginal damage. This especially applies to India (for both

167 NDC ambition levels) and to China (for the low NDC ambition level). Overall, the national carbon price
168 (= marginal abatement cost) falls short of the country-specific social cost of carbon in 69 and 65
169 countries under low NDC ambition levels, and in 40 and 39 countries under high NDC ambition levels,
170 for the DJO and Tol CSCC estimates, respectively. These countries would experience an economic gain
171 by increasing their emissions reductions ambitions, and thus should spend more on abatement efforts
172 for purely selfish reasons.

173

174 With full emissions trading, the average (emissions-weighted) CO₂ price falls from 26.46 (SD 18.00)
175 USD/tCO₂ to a market price of 9.64 (SD 5.11) USD/tCO₂ and from 42.08 (SD 20.76) USD/tCO₂ to 19.04
176 (SD 7.00) USD/tCO₂ for low and high ambition levels in the NDCs, respectively. So, even under high
177 ambition levels in the abatement levels, the market price falls short of the comparatively low Tol-SCC
178 estimate of 29.17 USD/tCO₂ (SD 9.70), indicating that under full emissions trading, the emissions
179 reduction levels should be increased under cost-benefit consideration.

180

181 If there was a global emissions trading scheme, for example, the United States and China would
182 become buyer and seller of international emissions reductions, respectively. Supplementary Figure
183 SMF1 shows the gains from emissions trading by equalizing marginal abatement costs for the United
184 States and China. Supplementary Figure SMF2 shows for the ten countries/regions with the largest
185 CO₂ emissions in the energy and industrial sector the costs of emissions reductions for high ambition
186 levels in the NDCs as percentage of their GDP. The full list of CO₂ price data and the costs of achieving
187 the NDCs as percentage of GDP (a negative entry indicates a gain) can be found in the Supplementary
188 Tables ST1 and ST2.

189

190 **2.3 Wealth contribution of the ocean carbon sink**

191 The wealth contribution of the annual global ocean carbon sink of 2.8 GtC, determined as its annual
192 contribution to comprehensive investment, ranges between USD 299.22 (SD 56.95) billion and USD
193 2,331.70 (SD 178.30) billion under the climate-change-damage based approach, using the Tol-CSCC
194 estimates and the DJO-CSCC estimates, respectively. Doing the same calculation, but using instead
195 abatement-based CO₂ prices, a global price is only obtained under the market solution (i.e. full trading)
196 and the annual value of the global ocean sink ranges between USD 99.00 (SD 52.55) billion and USD
197 195.39 (SD 72.14) billion, for NDCs with low and high ambition, respectively. In alternative scenarios,
198 we use national abatement-based CO₂ prices (i.e. there is no international emissions reductions
199 trading) to value the regional ocean carbon uptake. For example, using the model-based CO₂ price in
200 the EU, 101.51 (SD36.03) USD/tCO₂, implies a value of USD 55.70 (SD19.92) billion of the ocean carbon
201 sink attributed to the EU29. The aggregated value obtained when adding the national valuations is

202 USD 189.74 (SD 26.49) billion and USD 304.47 (SD 28.10) billion, for NDCs with low and high ambition,
203 respectively. While these estimates are higher than those obtained under a global CO₂ price, they
204 assign no value to regions without a CO₂ price. Most notably the value of the carbon sink in the high
205 seas is not taken into account in this approach.

206

207 **2.4 Balance of transboundary wealth contributions of the ocean carbon sink**

208 The climate-change-damage based approach allows quantification of the balance of transboundary
209 wealth contributions. While applying the (global) SCC yields insights into the global wealth
210 contribution of the ocean carbon sink in each nation's exclusive economic zone (a quantity OCS_i of
211 carbon absorbed per year by the water in the EEZ of country i), only a fraction of this contribution
212 accrues domestically. This fraction is calculated by valuing the domestic ocean carbon sink at the
213 domestic CSCC [13]. In addition, the domestic carbon sink generates wealth abroad, which is
214 calculated by applying the global SCC minus the domestic CSCC. However, at the same time, the ocean
215 sink in the waters of other countries, and in the high seas, also contribute to reducing climate change
216 impacts domestically. This is calculated by applying the domestic CSCC to the carbon sink in the ocean
217 everywhere except in domestic waters, $OCS - OCS_i$. Netting the outward wealth contribution of the
218 domestic ocean carbon sink with the inward wealth contribution of the non-domestic ocean carbon
219 sink determines the balance of transboundary wealth contribution. A positive (negative) balance
220 indicates that the ocean carbon sink attributed to the country contributes more (less) to foreign
221 wealth than the country receives from abroad. A positive balance in a given year, requires that

222

$$223 \frac{OCS_i}{OCS} > \frac{CSCC_i}{SCC}, \quad (1)$$

224

225 which means that the fraction of the annual ocean sink attributed to a given country relative to the
226 global ocean carbon sink (OCS_i/OCS) is greater than the fraction of the country's $CSCC_i$ relative to
227 the global SCC .

228

229 Since almost 60 percent of the annual carbon sink are attributed to the high seas, the individual shares
230 of countries, OCS_i/OCS , are rather small (the largest share is obtained by the EU29 with 5.35 percent,
231 only 1.96 percent without their oversea territories). Considering the total annual ocean carbon sink,
232 only 49 and 56 countries have a positive balance, using the Tol-CSCC estimates and the DJO-CSCC
233 estimates, respectively (the figures increase to 56 and 74 if countries are included with an attributed
234 ocean sink but with missing CSCC estimates, i.e. having a CSCC of zero). The largest wealth contribution

235 originates from the carbon sink attributed to the high sea, ranging between USD 175.53 (SD 33.41)
236 billion and USD 1,367.85 (SD 220.96) billion, for the Tol and DJO estimates, respectively.

237

238 Accordingly, we focus on the transboundary wealth contribution between countries, in dependence
239 of their share in the attributed ocean carbon sink without the carbon sink in the high seas (i.e.
240 OCS_i/OCS_{woHS}) and their shares of the global SCC (i.e., $CSCC_i/SCC$) in Figure 3. The figure shows
241 the implications of the different CSCC estimates, as the position on the x-axes, i.e. the share in the
242 attributed annual ocean carbon sink does not change between the upper and lower panel.
243 Accordingly, the color code indicates a positive (blue) and negative (orange) balance of transboundary
244 wealth contribution only for those countries with a clear assessment from both CSCC estimates while
245 countries where the assessment is not robust to the different CSCC estimates, i.e. with a positive
246 balance in the one study and negative balance in the other and vice versa, are indicated by a gray color
247 code. The visual difference between the two estimates is mainly explained by the estimates for the
248 United States and the EU29. According to the DJO-CSCC estimate, the combined share of United States
249 and EU29 at the global SCC is about 60 percent (with a share of 40 and 20 percent for the United States
250 and the EU29, respectively) while according to the Tol-CSCC estimate, the combined share is only
251 about 2 percent. In turn, with the DJO-CSCC estimates, these two regions are the main recipients of
252 the ocean carbon wealth contribution, i.e. having a negative balance, while both have a positive
253 balance under the Tol-CSCC estimates.

254

255 However, apart from these two extremely different assessments for the United States and the EU29,
256 a total of 87 out of 123 countries with an attributed ocean carbon sink have a clear assessment of the
257 balance of transboundary wealth contribution. If landlocked countries without an attributed ocean
258 sink are included, the number of countries with a clear assessment increase to 123. Under both
259 estimates, China has the largest negative balance, USD -43.04 (SD 22.29) billion and -14.74 (SD 8.05)
260 billion, decreasing to USD -116.00 (44.97) billion and USD -37.19 (SD 17.22) billion under the inclusion
261 of the contribution of the high seas, according to the DJO and Tol estimates, respectively. Also, under
262 both CSCC estimates, Australia has the largest positive balance, USD 37.87 (SD 9.73) billion and USD
263 7.35 (SD 1.24) billion, decreasing to USD 9.63 (SD 12.09) billion and USD 7.26 (SD 1.24) billion under
264 the inclusion of the contribution of the high seas, according to the DJO and Tol estimates, respectively.
265 The full list with the balance of transboundary wealth contribution for all countries, with and without
266 consideration of the carbon sink attributed to high sea, can be found in the Supplementary Results
267 ST3. The gains in domestic wealth contribution from the ocean carbon sink in oversea territories is
268 discussed in Supplementary Notes 1.

269

270 Figure3 about here

271

272 **2.5 Abatement costs implications from attributing ocean carbon sink**

273 We consider a scenario in which NDCs are increased in proportion to the attributed ocean carbon sink
274 to compensate for the weakening of the global ocean carbon sink. Accordingly, if the global ocean
275 carbon sink decreases by 5 percent (10 percent), countries' emission reduction targets are increased
276 by 13.5 per cent (27 percent) of their attributed ocean carbon sink. The relative increase in the NDC
277 reduction targets needs to be higher than the decrease in the global ocean carbon sink to compensate
278 also for reduction in the ocean carbon sink of the high seas. For example, a 5 percent (10 percent)
279 reduction in the global carbon sink implies that the EU29 would need to reduce its emissions by an
280 additional amount of about 74 (148) Mt CO₂.

281

282 Figure 4 shows the change in costs for a weakening of the global ocean carbon sink of 10 percent for
283 NDCs with high ambition levels under the assumption of no and full emissions reductions trading
284 (Panel a and b, respectively), displaying the ten major industrialized and developing regions in
285 international climate policy (Supplementary Figure SMF4 shows the corresponding information for
286 the countries and regions with the highest CO₂ emissions in the fossil and industrial sector).

287

288 Figure 4 about here

289

290 Without emissions reductions trading, for countries and regions with an attributed ocean carbon sink,
291 the abatement cost increase when the ocean carbon sink weakens (since they have to move up on the
292 marginal abatement cost curve, see Figure SMF2). For example, the cost of the EU29 increase from
293 0.23 (0.13) to 0.27 (SD 0.15) and 0.32 (SD 0.16) percent of its GDP in 2030, for a weakening of the global
294 ocean carbon sink of 5 and 10 percent, respectively. Now the ocean carbon sink in oversea territories
295 becomes an additional burden because without its oversea carbon sink attribution, the EU29 would
296 only need to increase its NDC by about 27 MtCO₂ and 54 MtCO₂ for a weakening of the global ocean
297 carbon sink of 5 and 10 percent, respectively. In turn, the cost of the EU29 would “only” increase from
298 0.23 (0.13) to 0.24 (SD 0.14) and 0.26 (SD 0.14) percent of its GDP in 2030, for a weakening of the
299 global ocean carbon sink of 5 and 10 percent, respectively.

300

301 For small island states with a relatively low GDP, but a relatively large EEZ and thus a large ocean
302 carbon sink, such a burden allocation in the event of a weakening of the ocean carbon sink would
303 impose a particular challenge. For example, for the Marshall Islands, the Maldives, and Nauru, the cost

304 increase to 5.65 (SD 0.78), 5.14 (SD 0.44), and 4.72 (SD 0.65) percent of their GDP for a weakening of
305 the global ocean sink by 10 percent.

306

307 Figure 4 shows that with emissions reductions trading (Panel b), some of the countries selling
308 emissions reductions would even gain from a weakening of the ocean carbon sink, as this would
309 increase demand for emission permits. This happens for countries with a rather flat marginal
310 abatement cost curve like China and/or with a relatively low ambition level in their NDCs like India.
311 This is because these countries can further decrease their emissions at low cost. If the international
312 price of CO₂ rises, these countries would increase their mitigation efforts and, in turn, their profits
313 from selling emission reductions, which may outweigh the additional costs of the NDC increase
314 resulting from the allocation of the burden of the weakening of the ocean carbon sink. Both, China
315 and India have a relatively small attributed ocean carbon sink, which means that they have to increase
316 their emissions reductions by only about 10 and 18 Mt CO₂, respectively, for a weakening of the global
317 ocean carbon sink of 10 percent. In turn, without emissions reduction trading, they have only a very
318 small increase in abatement cost even under high ambition NDCs (USD 0.06 and USD 0.01 billion,
319 respectively).

320

321 However, with emissions reduction trading, both China and India, which are the two largest emissions
322 reduction sellers, extend their sales volume from 1,647.52 (SD 449.00) and 936.65 (225.83) MtCO₂ to
323 1983.42 (SD 439.46) and 1012.63 (SD 223.57) MtCO₂, respectively, for a weakening of the global ocean
324 carbon sink of 10 percent and NDCs with high ambition. In this scenario, their net gains from climate
325 policy with emissions trading increase from 0.03 (SD 0.04) and 0.27 (SD 0.16) percent to 0.06 (SD 0.04)
326 and 0.34 (SD 0.19) percent of their GDP, respectively.

327

328 Supplementary Figure SMF5 shows how aggregated abatement costs and global CO₂ prices increase
329 under the assumption of high ambition NDCs for scenarios without and with international emissions
330 trading, for a gradual weakening of the global carbon sink by up to 10 percent. Without international
331 emissions reductions trading, the global CO₂ price is the emissions-weighted average of the national
332 CO₂ prices. Without emissions reductions trading, the global aggregated costs increase by 30 percent,
333 from USD 262.34 (SD 42.99) to USD 341.83 (SD 49.43) billion, with emissions reduction trading, the
334 global aggregated costs increase by 28 percent, from USD 57.12 (SD 23.21) billion to USD 72.91 (SD
335 27.00), in both scenarios under the assumption of NDCs with high ambition.

336

337 The CO₂ price and its response due to the allocation of additional reduction requirements provides
338 information on the incentives to include (marine) CDR. Assuming a weakening of the ocean carbon
339 sink and the suggested allocation of additional emissions reductions, the national CO₂ prices in three
340 potential large CDR markets, the United States., EU29, and Japan, increases from USD/tCO₂ 55.81 (SD
341 22.61), 101.51 (SD 36.03), and 151.67. (SD 46.24) to USD/tCO₂ 63.25 (SD 23.43), 129.95 (37.80), and
342 169.48 (SD 46.41), respectively. Accordingly, the economic prospects of marine CDR methods like
343 marine biomass farming and harvesting or ocean alkalinity enhancement would increase under such
344 an allocation of the liability for the ocean carbon sink. However, our calculation show that such prices
345 would only be realized on national markets and that the efficient approach to increase the reduction
346 levels in the NDCs like for example to compensate the weakening of the ocean carbon sink would be
347 to extend the scope of international emissions reductions trading. The full country list for CO₂ prices
348 and the costs of achieving the NDCs as percentage of GDP under attenuated ocean carbon sink of 5
349 and 10 percent can be found in the Supplementary Results ST1 and ST2, respectively.

350 **3 Discussion and Conclusions**

351 The United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, coordinated by
352 Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC), aims at a "predicted ocean where society
353 understands and can respond to changing ocean conditions" [21, p.8]. One key ocean service is
354 removing anthropogenic CO₂ from the atmosphere. In turn, changing net ocean uptake, for example
355 as a consequence of a decrease in the physical carbon pump [22], would be a changing ocean condition
356 relevant for society. Accordingly, calls to expand the global (carbon) ocean observing system would
357 be better able to substantiate their claim with information on the value of the ocean sink.

358
359 We combine a climate-change-damage-based approach and an abatement-cost-based approach to
360 assess the value of the annual ocean sink. For the former, we include in our assessment the estimates
361 of Ricke et al. [23,24], while restricting it to the climate change impact function provided by Dell et al.
362 [19] due to conceptual problems with the other impact function in that study [20, 25, 26], obtaining
363 an average SCC of USD/tCO₂ 227.28 (SD 14.95). We compare these estimates with Tol et al. [20]; his
364 estimates add up to USD/tCO₂ 29.17 (SD 3.67). We do not aggregate the two SCC estimates, because
365 they rely on very different assumptions, but instead provide the estimates separately, highlighting the
366 unresolved uncertainties in terms of quantifying the impacts of climate change. The CSCC estimates
367 can be compared at the SCC level (i.e. the sum of the CSCCs) to recent estimates for the SCC in the
368 literature. Kalkuhl and Wenz [27] find an empirically derived estimated range for the SCC (in the year
369 2030) from USD/tCO₂ 92 to 181, the former obtained under a cross-section estimate, the latter under
370 a population-based panel estimate. Similarly, Rennert et al. [28] derive a model-based estimate for

371 the SCC of USD/tCO₂ 185 (44–413, 5%–95% range). In turn the higher SCC estimate, obtained based
372 on [19] appears to be better supported by the literature, yet, the estimates of Tol [20] are not
373 disproved. In our assessment of transboundary wealth transfers, we showed that large part of the
374 difference between the two assessments are based on differences in the estimation for the United
375 States and the EU29. Apart from these two extremely different assessments, 87 out of 123 countries
376 with an attributed ocean carbon sink have a clear assessment of the balance of transboundary wealth
377 contribution. Under both estimates, China has the largest negative balance and Australia has the
378 largest positive balance.

379

380 With respect to the abatement-cost-based approach we calibrated a global CO₂ market model with
381 defined emissions reduction targets. A previous meta-study provided by Böhringer et al. [18] finds a
382 range for the emissions-weighted global average CO₂ price from USD/tCO₂ 12.66 to 42.86 for
383 implementing the NDCs in 2030. The emissions-weighted global average CO₂ prices in our study are
384 USD/tCO₂ 26.46 (SD 18.00) and 42.08 (SD 20.79) for low and high emissions reduction ambition levels
385 as defined in the NDCs. Despite the relatively good fit with other studies, it should be acknowledged
386 that such computable general equilibrium models aggregate several countries to regions and consider
387 only some (economically) large countries like China, the United States, Germany and India separately,
388 while many countries (in particular developing countries in Africa, Asia and Latin America) are
389 aggregated. The DART model underlying our estimate provides results for 21 regions, which we break
390 down to the country level, assuming that within a given region, a country with low emissions efficiency
391 (i.e., a high emissions-to-GDP ratio) has lower abatement costs than countries which already have a
392 higher emissions efficiency. However, for large DART regions like Africa, this seems to be a strong
393 assumption and hence our results for economically small countries, many of which have comparatively
394 large, attributed ocean carbon sinks, should be considered with caution. On the other hand, the model
395 underlying our calibration implicitly assumes emissions trading across all sectors within the
396 (aggregated) regions, i.e., ignoring the fragmentation and various frictions of national climate policies.
397 Accordingly, the estimated abatement-cost based CO₂-prices are lower than observed, actual and in
398 particular implicit CO₂-prices resulting from regulations and provisions in national climate policies [29,
399 30].

400

401 Generally speaking, the climate-change-damage-based assessment approach allows to value the
402 ocean sink from an inclusive wealth perspective. Agreeing on an attribution of the ocean carbon sink
403 to countries or regions allows then to obtain further insights in the balance of transboundary wealth
404 contributions. This requires though a discussion which fraction of the biological, chemical, and physical

405 mechanism underlying the global ocean carbon sink (e.g., [31]) should be considered in the attribution
406 to countries. Abatement-cost-based approaches, despite the uncertainty about innovations in
407 emission abatement technologies, appear to yield a narrower range if applied to the valuation of the
408 ocean carbon sink. Accordingly, we suggest that for questions related to for example spending to
409 improve the monitoring of the ocean carbon sink, the abatement-cost-based approach provides more
410 reliable estimates for a fiscal cost assessment. Furthermore, the abatement-cost-based approach
411 provides a framework to assess the implications of a (partly) integration of the ocean carbon sink into
412 climate policy. Any attribution of the ocean carbon sink does not necessarily imply a potential buy-
413 out from ambitious emissions reductions, as the implications for emissions reduction commitments
414 depend on the particular baseline level considered for the ocean carbon sink. One could argue that
415 the current NDCs are derived in dependence of the current and future carbon sinks, i.e., they are net
416 of the natural CO₂ uptake by the terrestrial biosphere and the ocean. Accordingly, any weakening of
417 the natural sinks would need to be compensated by increasing the ambition level in the NDCs. Such
418 considerations could guide the question of which aspects and which fraction of the ocean carbon sink
419 in general and which fraction of the overseas territories should be attributed to countries, in order to
420 link attribution and thus potential wealth contributions also with potential emission reductions and
421 possible CDR liabilities.

422

423 **Methods**

424 **The attribution of the sink**

425 While the ocean carbon sink is a global common, the ocean-atmosphere CO₂ fluxes differ considerably
426 across the globe. Using regional CO₂-flux data for example would result in assigning some countries a
427 carbon sink and others a carbon source, i.e. not an ecosystem service but an ecosystem burden. For
428 example, the highest carbon source (outgassing) would be attributed to Kiribati (KIR), an island nation
429 in the tropical Pacific Ocean, with approximately 726 km² land area and a 3,550,000-km² EEZ located
430 in the Pacific upwelling area. Almost all of Kiribati's waters are considered to be carbon sources (based
431 on the surface pCO₂ field estimate used here) and would contribute a negative value, i.e., a global cost
432 if the country were held responsible for its ocean carbon fluxes. However, such an approach would
433 mix the natural with the anthropogenic carbon fluxes. The latter is the consequence of increasing
434 atmospheric CO₂ concentration and in turn all ocean regions are taking up anthropogenic carbon by
435 being at the regional level a lower carbon source than they were under preindustrial levels, by turning
436 from a carbon source to a carbon sink, or increasing the carbon sink compared to preindustrial levels.
437 Since a preindustrial benchmark for these flux data is missing, we use the model-based derived global
438 ocean CO₂ sink of 2.8 (SD ±0.4) Gt C (in the year 2022) from the global carbon budget [1] and assign it
439 proportional to the EEZ area of countries [32]. We abstract from issues related to temporary carbon
440 storage since we consider the accounting of the carbon sink at the country and not the company level,
441 implying that a strong liability framework is in place and that in turn the net method can be applied to
442 carbon sink in a given year [33]. The attributed ocean carbon sink is detailed in Supplementary Data
443 M1.

444

445 **Estimating the wealth contribution of the annual ocean carbon sink**

446 We applied the inclusive wealth approach and calculated the annual global wealth contribution of the
447 ocean carbon sink in the EEZ of each country *i* in given year, i.e. the annual contribution to global
448 comprehensive investment as

$$449 W_{i,global} = OSC_i * SCC \text{ with } SCC = \sum_i CSCC_i, \quad (2)$$

450

451 where *OSC_i* indicates the ocean carbon sink in the EEZ (measured in tCO₂/year) and *SCC* is the (global)
452 social cost of carbon, which is the sum of *CSCC_i*, i.e., the country social cost of carbon (measured in
453 USD/tCO₂) [11, 13].

454

455 Using *CSCC* estimates allowed us to distinguish between domestic, outbound and inbound wealth
456 contributions of the ocean carbon sink [13]. The domestic ocean carbon wealth contribution is:

457

458 $W_{i,domestic} = OCS_i * CSCC_i,$ (3)

459

460 the outbound ocean carbon wealth contribution is:

461

462 $W_{i,out} = OCS_i * (\sum_{j \neq i} CSCC_j),$ (4)

463

464 and the inbound ocean carbon wealth contribution for country i is:

465

466 $W_{i,in} = (\sum_{j \neq i} OCS_j) * CSCC_i.$ (5)

467

468 The balance of transboundary wealth contributions of the ocean carbon sink (in a given year) is the

469 difference between outbound and inbound ocean carbon wealth contributions [13]:

470

471 $BTWC_i = OCS_i * (\sum_{j \neq i} CSCC_j) - (\sum_{j \neq i} OCS_j) * CSCC_i$ (6)

472

473 which can be simplified to

474

475 $BTWC_i = OCS_i * SCC - OCS_i * CSCC_i.$ (7)

476

477 Accordingly, a positive balance of transboundary wealth contributions by the ocean sink in a given

478 year requires that $\frac{OCS_i}{OCS} > \frac{CSCC_i}{SCC}$, (see equation 1 in the main text) which means that the fraction of

479 the annual ocean sink attributed to a given country relative to the global ocean carbon sink is

480 greater than the fraction of the country's CSCC relative to the global SCC.

481

482 **Deriving climate-change-damage-based prices**

483 We obtained estimates from the literature for the CSCC from Ricke et al. [23, 24] and Tol [20] whereby

484 the former has two different climate-damage function groups, one provided by Burke et al. [34] and

485 one provided by Dell et al. [19]; we used only those CSCC estimates based on the damage impact

486 function put forward by Dell et al.[19], which yields (i) a smaller (negative) impact for rich countries,

487 (ii) has a linear specification for the change in temperature, (iii) does not have a U-shaped impact

488 projection towards 2100 for global impacts and is therefore more in line with macroeconomic impact

489 estimates of climate change [26]. Furthermore, the specification of Burke et al. [34] implies due to the

490 persistent impacts of climate change on growth that cumulative gains of the countries with

491 accelerated growth (climate change winners) start to outweigh the cumulative losses of countries who
492 lose from climate change towards the end of the century.

493

494 The estimation strategy put forward by Ricke et al. [23, 24] includes all SSPs and considers three RCPs:
495 RCP45, RCP60 and RCP85. From these scenarios, we used the scenarios obtained for RCP60, as here
496 the emissions were comparable to the baseline emissions in Tol [20] and considered the scenarios
497 with a pure rate of time preference of 1 percent and a marginal elasticity of utility of 1.5 (of the
498 different SSPs). The estimates in Ricke et al. [23, 24] are presented in USD PPP (2005); hence we
499 converted these two market exchange values and used the GDP deflator (both obtained from the
500 World Bank) to obtain estimates in 2020 USD. Based on this approach, we obtained an average SCC
501 (across the different SSPs) of USD/tCO₂ 227.28 (SD 14.95).

502

503 Tol [20] provides estimates for the impact of climate change on the level of economic activity for
504 different impact functions. We used the estimates obtained from the Tol impact function for the
505 different SSPs and a pure rate of time preference of 1 percent and income elasticity of impacts
506 of -1.68. The estimates are provided by [19] in 2010 USD at market exchange rates. We used the
507 USD GDP deflator to convert the estimates into 2020 USD and obtained an average SCC (across the
508 five SSPs) of USD/tCO₂ 29.17 (SD 3.67). The obtained estimates for the CSCC and the corresponding
509 wealth analysis is detailed in Supplementary Data M2.

510

511 **Deriving abatement-cost-based prices**

512 We used the Dynamic Applied Regional Trade (DART) model to estimate marginal abatement cost
513 curves, providing information on the abatement-cost-based CO₂ price for a given emissions reduction
514 level. DART is a global and recursive dynamic computable general equilibrium (CGE) model [35, 36].
515 The advantage of using a global CGE model lies in its ability to capture not just the direct domestic
516 multiplier effects of a carbon price but also indirect implications via changes in international energy
517 prices and trade flows [35]. Given that economic structures vary across regions, marginal abatement
518 costs differ widely across regions and therefore need to be calculated individually.

519

520 We calibrated the DART model to the GTAP10 database [37] with 2014 as the base year and the
521 baseline dynamics calibrated to the GDP data from IEA [38] and updated to include renewable energy
522 data from the IEA [39]. With this updated model, marginal abatement cost curves (MACC) for the year
523 2030 were generated separately for each model region by varying the emissions reduction target of
524 said region between 0% reduction theoretically up to 100% (relative to 2014 levels) in increments of

525 5% while assuming that the rest of the regions fulfilled their national determined contribution (NDC)
 526 targets [18].

527

528 Based on this approach, for each region i , we created cubic abatement cost curves, $AC_i(E_i)$, which
 529 imply quadratic marginal abatement cost curves, and $MAC_i(E_i)$ to the modelled values where E_i
 530 represents the actual 2030 emissions in the reduction scenario. Let $E_{i,BAU}$ denote the 2030 emissions
 531 in the business-as-usual (BAU) scenario without climate policy and $Y_{i,BAU}$ GDP in 2030, then

$$532 \quad AC_i(E_i) = \alpha_i * \left(1 - \frac{E_i}{E_{i,BAU}}\right)^3 Y_{i,BAU} E_{i,BAU} \quad (8)$$

$$533 \quad MAC_i(E_i) = \frac{dAC_i(E_i)}{-dE_i} = \alpha_i * 3 * \left(1 - \frac{E_i}{E_{i,BAU}}\right)^2 Y_{i,BAU} \quad (9)$$

534

535 Note that the marginal abatement costs (MAC) are defined by the derivate with respect to minus E_i
 536 since they measure how the abatement cost increase if abatement is increased, i.e. emissions are
 537 reduced.

538

539 The abatement cost parameters were determined by solving the following minimization problem

$$540 \quad \min_{\alpha_i} \sum \left(P_{CO_2^{DART}} - (3\alpha_i R_i^2 Y_{i,BAU}) \right)^2. \quad (10)$$

541

542 Thus, the cost parameters α_i were calibrated by minimizing the sum of the difference between the
 543 CO₂ price $P_{CO_2^{DART}}$ and the CO₂ price following from the condition (9). To obtain country-specific
 544 abatement cost functions for the DART regions with more than one country, we used the approach
 545 proposed by Tol [40] and assumed a 10-percent spread in relative costs between the country with the
 546 highest carbon intensity (CO₂/GDP) and the country with the lowest carbon intensity for a 10-percent
 547 reduction. The calibration details can be found in Supplementary Data M3.

548

549 To quantify abatement costs, we drew on the latest information on the Nationally Determined
 550 Contributions (NDCs) from Climate Resource, who provide an NDC database covering each country's
 551 initial NDC and the development of its climate policy over time [41]. The dataset includes all NDC
 552 updates submitted up to November 2nd, 2022. The NDCs vary in their commitment levels depending
 553 on the emissions reductions of other countries. We extracted the updated covered GHG data for low
 554 and high ambition targets, respectively. Hot air was included; emissions from the LULUCF sector were
 555 not. For both high and low ambitions, the target emissions from 2030 and 2020 were set in ratio. With
 556 respect to the BAU emissions in 2030, the low emissions-reduction ambitions imply a reduction of
 557 16.22 (SD 4.28) percent, while the high emissions-reduction ambitions imply a reduction of 23.16 (SD
 558 4.16) percent.

559

560 Furthermore, information on business-as-usual GDP, $Y_{i,BAU}$ and 2030 business-as-usual CO₂ emissions,
561 $E_{i,BAU}$ was obtained from the DART model and we considered the projections for all SSPs in the
562 baseline (marker) specification [42] together with the OECD GDP growth projections [43]. Hence, we
563 considered a total of six scenarios for future GDP and emissions. We transformed this data into values
564 relative to the base year in the specific scenario and used data on GDP from the World Bank [44] and
565 on CO₂ emissions from the Global Carbon Project [1] in 2020 as the common base year values. For
566 each scenario, we calculated the marginal abatement cost for the low and high emissions-reduction
567 targets.

568

569 The MACCs also allowed us to derive a market solution, i.e., countries trade emissions reductions.
570 Accordingly, we used the MACCs in the following model framework. The countries, i , face an
571 exogenously set emissions cap A_i (provided by the NDCs). Without emissions reductions, business-as-
572 usual emissions are realized, $E_{i,BAU}$. The total amount of emissions by each country, E_i , is non-
573 negative and no country can abate more than it emits,

$$574 \quad 0 \leq E_i \leq E_{i,BAU}. \quad (11)$$

575 We allowed for a market on tradable emissions reduction permits, where the permit price is
576 represented by π and the number of permits each country purchases or sells by T_i . In order to fulfill
577 the emissions target, every country can reduce its baseline emissions and trade permits on the market.
578 Thus, the difference between emissions and the number of permits must not exceed the emissions
579 cap,

580

$$581 \quad E_i - T_i \leq A_i. \quad (12)$$

582

583 The total cost of achieving a given target A_i is determined by the sum of abatement and permit trading
584 costs (or trading benefits if a country is a net seller of permits, $T_i < 0$). Therefore, each country solves
585 the following optimization problem,

586

$$587 \quad \min_{R_i, T_i} C_i = AC_i(R_i) + \pi T_i, \quad (13)$$

588

589 subject to equation (12). Solving the static optimization problem, assuming an interior solution, yields
590 the well-known efficiency rule that for all countries, the marginal cost of abatement equals the permit
591 price,

592

593 $AC'(E_i^*) = \pi.$ (14)

594

595 The market allocates the permits efficiently. Condition (14) shows that the optimal rate of emissions
596 reduction can be expressed as a function of the carbon credit price, $E_i^*(\pi)$. The optimal permit price
597 can be determined using the overall compliance condition,

598

599 $\sum_i^n E_i^*(\pi^*) = \sum_i^n A_i,$ (15)

600

601 which states that the sum of all countries' net emissions equals the sum of all countries' emissions
602 caps. With the functional form defined in (8), the solution for the permit price is

603

604 $\pi = \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n E_{i,BAU} - \sum_{i=1}^n A_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n E_{i,BAU} \sqrt{(3\alpha_i Y_i)^{-1}}} \right)^2$ (16)

605

606 which then determines via (14) and (12) the country-specific emissions levels and trading positions.

607 The inclusion of the ocean sink (i.e., a compensation for a weakening ocean sink) is achieved by
608 reducing each country's A_i accordingly. In both solutions, the market solution (full CO₂ trade) in
609 comparison to the no trade solution, the CO₂-price shows the maximum cost at which a specific
610 (marine) CDR method would need to be realized to be cost-competitive [45]. The two solutions are
611 detailed in Supplementary Data M4.

612 **Data Availability Statement**

613 The authors declare that the data on the attribution of the sink, the derivation of the CO₂ prices, the
614 inclusive wealth contribution and redistribution, the calibration of the CO₂ abatement-cost model,
615 and the country-specific abatement costs is included in the GitHub repository
616 <https://github.com/wilmwilmsen/OceanValue>.

617
618 **Competing interests**

619 The authors declare no competing interests.

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630 **Author Contributions**

631 W.R., F.M., M.Q.: conception and design of the work, analysis and interpretation of data, writing
632 original draft and review and editing; J.K.: analysis, acquisition, collection, and interpretation of data,
633 writing original draft; S.P., S.R., S.T., C.P., C.W., A.V., and P.G.: analysis, acquisition, collection, and
634 interpretation of data. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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747
748

749 Figure Captions

750

751 **Figure 1: The 10 states (or confederation of states) with the largest attribution of the annual ocean**
752 **sink.** We distinguish between domestic attribution and attribution resulting from oversea territories.
753 Error bars represent ± 1 SD of domestic and oversea territories attributed ocean sink. EU29, European
754 Union 27 plus Norway and Iceland; USA, United States; AUS, Australia; GBR, Great Britain; RUS, Russia;
755 IDN, Indonesia; CAN, Canada; NZL, New Zealand; JPN, Japan; KIR, Kiribati.

756

757 **Figure 2: National and global CO₂ prices.** The bars show the national abatement-based CO₂ prices
758 estimates (i.e., without international emissions trading) for NDCs with low and high ambition levels,
759 respectively, and national damage-based CO₂ prices estimates, (i.e., country social cost of carbon
760 (CSCC)), obtained from Dell et al. [18] in Ricke et al. [22, 23], abbreviated as DJO, and obtained from
761 Tol [19], abbreviated Tol, respectively. The vertical lines show the global abatement-based CO₂ price
762 estimates (i.e. with international emissions trading), for NDCs with low and high ambition levels,
763 respectively, and the global damage-based CO₂ estimates (i.e., social cost of carbon SCC), for the DJO
764 and Tol estimate, respectively. Error bars represent ± 1 SD for the national CO₂ prices. The figure
765 includes the ten major industrialized and developing regions in international climate policy. Countries
766 are indicated by their ISO3 code: CHN, China; USA, United States, EU29, European Union 27 with
767 Norway and Iceland; IND, India; RUS, Russia; JPN, Japan; KOR, South Korea; CAN, Canada; BRA,
768 Brazilian; AUS, Australia.

769

770 **Figure 3: Balance of transboundary wealth contribution of countries.** The upper panels (a and aa)
771 show the wealth contribution based on the CSCC estimates obtained from Dell et al. [18] in Ricke et
772 al. [22, 23], abbreviated as DJO, whereby Panel a shows all countries and Panel aa shows an
773 enlargement of the countries near the origin, which are located in the dashed box in Panel a. The
774 lower panels (b and bb) show the wealth contribution based on the CSCC estimates obtained from Tol
775 [19], abbreviated Tol, whereby Panel b shows all countries and Panel bb shows an enlargement of the
776 countries near the origin, which are located in the dashed box in Panel b. The x-axes show the share
777 of country in the total annual carbon, excluding the ocean carbon sink attributed to the high seas
778 (C_i/C_{woHS}), the y-axes show the share of CSCC of country i in the social cost of carbon ($CSCC_i/SCC$).
779 The color code indicates a positive (blue) and negative (orange) balance for countries with a clear
780 assessment from both CSCC estimates while countries where the assessment is not robust to the
781 different CSCC estimates, are indicated by a gray color code. Countries are indicated by their ISO3
782 code: AFG, Afghanistan; AUS, Australia; BGD, Bangladesh; BRA, Brazil; CAN, Canada; CHE, Switzerland;
783 CHL, Chile; CHN, China; COD, Congo; COK, Cook Islands; EGY, Egypt; ETH, Ethiopia; EU29, European
784 Union 27 plus Iceland and Norway; GBR, United Kingdom; IDN, Indonesia; IND, India; JPN, Japan; KEN,

785 Kenya; KIR, Kiribati; KOR, South Korea; MDG, Madagascar; MEX, Mexico; MHL, Marshall Islands; MOZ,
786 Mozambique; MWI, Malawi; NER, Niger; NGA, Nigeria; NPL, Nepal; NZL, New Zealand; PAK, Pakistan;
787 PHL, Philippines; PNG, Papua New Guinea; RUS, Russia; SAU, Saudi Arabia; SLB, Solomon Islands; TUR,
788 Turkey; TZA, Tanzania; UGA, Uganda; USA, United States; VNM, VietNam; ZAF, South Africa.

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790 **Figure 4: Cost implications of the weakening of the ocean carbon sink for national climate policies.**

791 The figure shows the change in costs (or gains in case of a negative cost) from a weakening of the
792 global ocean carbon sink by 5 and 10 percent for a scenario without emissions reductions trading
793 (Panel a) and for a scenario with full emissions reductions trading (Panel b). The figure includes the
794 ten major industrialized and developing regions in international climate policy. Error bars represent
795 ± 1 SD for the national CO₂ prices. Countries are indicated by their ISO3 code: CHN, China; USA, United
796 States, EU29, European Union 27 with Norway and Iceland; IND, India; RUS, Russia; JPN, Japan; KOR,
797 South Korea; CAN, Canada; BRA, Brazilian; AUS, Australia.

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